

School Based Management: A 21st Century Approach to School Development

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ABSTRACT

Public school education across the world has undergone trends where the school management shifts from centralization and decentralization. This research has focused on a variety of the best strategies and practices of school based management in a global approach. The findings of this study showed that there are different indicators emerged as significant in relation to School based management. These include the effective school leadership, management strategies, faculty development, and stakeholders' participation were identified that have huge influence in attaining the overall objectives and aims of school based management. Based on the data gathered, there were no single formula in achieving the overall goal of our school based management, however, there are number of practices that leads to positive and quality educational system these includes effective leadership, management strategies, faculty development and stakeholders participation. Therefore, with these practices, there is a huge probability that a school will likely achieve its goal.

KEYWORDS: School Based Management, Effective Leadership, Stakeholders, Strategies

INTRODUCTION

Education across the world has experienced periodic trends where the school management emphasis shifted from centralization to decentralization influenced by the modern management in industrial and commercial organizations. The dissatisfaction with the important method of training and the move toward decentralization delivered various faculty reform movements, all of which aimed toward improving performance, fairness, and fine of education. Many researchers confirm that one of the maximum tremendous reforms inside the cutting-edge restructuring of school structures has been the devolution of choice-making authority to school levels through school based management (Zajda & Gamage, 2009; Caldwell, 2005; Ogawa & White, 1994; Cheng Cheong, 1996). School-based management (SBM) has been a major part of the education reform movement over the past three decades. It is a form of decentralization that identifies individual school as the primary unit of improvement and relies on the redistribution of decision-making Authority as the primary means through which improvement may be stimulated and sustained (Malen et al. 1990)

Moreover, education system is managed by different methods throughout the world; including centralized, semi centralized and decentralized methods that are administrated through different systems. Among such

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systems School-Based Management (SBM) based on decentralized method could be mentioned (Moradi et al. 2012).

Concepts of School Based Management

The world that surrounds us has changed. This change has forced organizations, including educational organizations to redesign themselves to ensure their prosperity in the twenty-first century environment (Abdulla and Al Kaabi, 2015).

Pang (2007) noted that school based management usually involves the creation of school site councils and the decentralization of power and/or school budget to the school sites either from the central/state Government (e.g., New Zealand, Australia) or school district/local education authority (e.g., USA, UK).

Caldwell (2005) stated that School-based management is the systematic decentralization to the school level of authority and responsibility to make decisions on significant matters related to school operations within a centrally determined framework of goals, policies, curriculum, standards, and accountability. Moreover, governments around the world are introducing a range of strategies aimed at improving the financing and delivery of education services, with a more

recent emphasis on improving quality as well as increasing quality in education. One such strategy is to decentralize education decision-making by increasing parental and community involvement in schools—which is popularly known as school-based management (SBM). The argument in favor of SBM is that decentralizing decision-making authority to parents and communities fosters demand and ensures that schools provide the social and economic benefits that best reflect the priorities and values of those local communities (Lewis, 2006; and Leithwood and Menzies, 1998). Education reforms in Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries tend to share some common characteristics of this kind, including increased school autonomy, greater responsiveness to local needs, and the overall objective of improving students' academic performance (OECD, 2004). Most countries whose students perform well in international student achievement tests give local authorities and schools substantial autonomy to decide the content of their curriculum and the allocation and management of their resources. An increasing number of developing countries are introducing SBM reforms aimed at empowering principals and teachers or at strengthening their professional motivation, thereby enhancing their sense of ownership of the school. Many of these reforms have also strengthened parental involvement in the schools, sometimes by means of school councils (Wordbank, 2007). Further, the basic framework of quality education is one that achieved its desires and goals and one that is relevant to the desires of schools, communities and society; and one that fosters the capacity of students to collect expertise and the needed twenty first century skills (Stone, Bruce & Hursh, 2007).

Importance of School Based Management

School-based management has been institutionalized in places like England, where more than 25,000 schools have had experience with the practice for more than a decade; or like New Zealand or Victoria, Australia or in several large school systems in Canada and the United States, where there has been experience for similar lengths of time. The practice seems irreversible in these settings. An indication of the scale and scope of interest in school based management was provided at the 3rd APEC Education Ministerial Meeting in Santiago, Chile in April 2004. APEC (Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation) is a network of 21 economies that together contain about one-third of the world's population. The theme of the meeting was "quality in education" and governance was one of four sub-themes. Particular attention was given to decentralization. Ministers endorsed school-based management as a strategy in educational reform but also endorsed aspects of centralization, such as frameworks for accountability. They acknowledged that arrangements in different economies should vary, reflecting the uniqueness of each setting (Caldwell, 2005).

Quality isn't always the most component maintaining students out of school, but while effective learning isn't always taking location in faculties. Whilst this happens, numerous elements can be regarded as motives: poor teaching-gaining knowledge of experience given through instructors, having incompetent school inside the rosters of teachers, mismanaged school system by school heads, and negative management capability and erroneous governance of the school administrator (Grauwe, 2004).

Velasco (2012) noted that over the years, the academic system has been undergoing rehabilitation and development to keep tempo with the international developments in training. Regions like exceptional and excellence, relevance and responsiveness, get right of entry to and fairness and performance and effectiveness in faculty management and administration are the principle awareness of evaluation and assessment and steady re-assessment. As such, rules and processes in addition to structures of the educational resources bring about the non-stop modifications of the educational systems.

School-based management has many shades of meaning. It has been implemented in different ways and for different reasons and at different rates in different settings. Even the more fundamental concepts of "school" and "management" are different, as are the cultures and values that underpin the efforts of policy makers and practitioners. However, the common ground in all places where school based management has been implemented is that there has been an increase in authority and responsibility at the school level, but within a centrally-determined framework that ensures that a sense of system is sustained.

The road to decentralization within the Philippine education system started at some stage in the Marcos time. It changed into similarly reinforced with the aid of instructional Act of 1982 with the aid of giving the department of schooling the bureaucratic autonomy to formulate plan, and implement academic guidelines and improvements in any respect levels. Local government Code of 1991 paved the manner for extra decentralization because it accelerated the participation of stakeholders in training Velasco (2012) However, De Guzman (2007) revealed that the Philippine educational system, just like the systems of education among developing countries, are plague by restraining trends like low performance of students, recurrent shortages, myopic view of the system, unmotivated teachers and principals, low accountability level and poor monitoring and evaluation level. This led to the adoption of policy on authority and power-sharing to facilitate self-management and improved decision making processes to address these restraining trends. De Guzman further noted that one of these megatrends is decentralization of school management which came to be known as school based management.

Background of the study

School Based Management is guided by different theories and its importance in improving learning outcomes. Involvement of the school-based management stakeholders in the school governance ensures sustainable inter-dependent relationship between the school and the community, by promoting good value system and recognizing the cooperation, participation and support of significant and relevant stakeholders in the setting of standards and ensuring quality in the management of school resources. This dynamic process of relationship strengthens the community intervention and mandate in education and instills sense of collective ownership, responsibility and commitment to the progress of the school's programs, activities, development of physical structures, learning facilities and improvement in learning outcome (Ayeni, 2010). There has been growing realization among school-based management proponents that a major reason proposing SBM is the achievement of better student results.

This might explain why “most governments have adopted it as part of their educational reform policies (Caldwell, 2005). Many scholars also affirm that the movement toward school-based management is often assumed as the approach to serve the students better by “improving the school practices in meeting the diverse expectations of the stakeholders in a changing environment toward increasing student achievement and performance” (Anderson, 2006). In his study concludes that greater school autonomy has a positive impact on the teaching-learning environment and students’ achievement.

Objective of the study

Given the related studies and research findings above, finding have indicated the importance of school based management in achieving the schools objectives. Hence, this research review would find out the best practices and strategies employed and introduce in different schools across the world. This led to the researchers the idea that school based management is a must and a need to revisit most specially to the trends and improvement of school based management.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Effective School leadership

Highly effective school leadership is one of the most significant influences on student progress, wellbeing and success. Supporting and promoting student wellbeing. Regular planning and evaluating of teaching practice to ensure that the school is meeting the learning needs of all students (NZG, 2016).

Figure1. Leadership

Figure 1 shows the results of effective leadership in relation to school based management practices. Based on the data gathered, goal-reference got the highest rank which means that defining goals is very necessary to achieve the schools objectives in accordance to the school based management. According to Room (2013) revealed that someone who is goal-referenced has a clearly defined goal to which they are committed and will take action to achieve it. The information collected from those actions often reveal whether the decisions they made in pursuit of the goal were the best or if an alternate course would be more successful the next time. School leadership feedback must be clear in relaying their goals or the goals being set will not be achieved which is demoralizing. Therefore, to fully implement the school based management leaders must extend and define the goal that they need to attain so that everyone can participate and do their parts.

Management strategies

Strategic Management is the transformation of school management performed by the stakeholders (Wooi, 2017).

Figure2. Strategy

Strategy is important to an organization because it can provide an overall strategic direction to the management of the organization and gives a specific direction to areas like financial strategy, marketing strategy, organizational development strategy and human resource strategy, to achieve in execution (Verma, 2016). Figure 2 shows the strategies that school leaders utilize. The results shows that involvement of stakeholders is very fundamentals in achieving the overall outcome of the school based management. Pelayo (2018) stated stakeholders play an important role in managing schools. They are the partners of the schools conducive to teaching and learning. Resources of the organization have also identified as important factors in attaining the overall objectives of SBM and environment the place of the quality involvement of different stakeholders. According to Chua (2019) if your environment is not conducive toward achieving your goals, you will be wasting a lot of energy trying to go against it every day. Hence, a conducive environment would likely achieve the goals and objectives of the school.

Faculty development

The faculty development plan is a "blueprint" describing a faculty member's proposed professional activities. Resources needed to accomplish the professional goals, including budgetary support, equipment, time, etc. (FAC, 2019).

Figure3. Faculty Development

According to Kamel (2016) faculty development has been defined as that wide range of activities that institutions apply to support faculty members' roles. This included programs designed to improve the performance

of faculty members in education, research and administration as well as augmenting organizational capacities and culture. Figure 3 shows the data that relates faculty development and school based management. The data shows that faculty development has influence the involvement of the faculty. This indicates that through faculty development, it can elevate the overall performance and participation of the faculty in relation to SBM. Therefore, there must have an appropriate training given to the faculty in order for them to fully understand the basic tenet of school based management.

Stakeholders Participation

The stakeholders play an important role in managing schools. They are the partners of the school leaders in making the schools conducive to teaching and learning (Pelayo, 2018).

**Figure 4
Stakeholders**

Figure 4 shows the importance of stakeholders participation in achieving the attainment of schools objectives and aims. Cabardo (2016) on his study indicated that the indicates and shows that the level of participation of stakeholders in the different school-initiated activities can be affected by the level of implementation of school-based management. This implies that a higher level of implementation of school-based management would indicate a higher level of participation of stakeholders in the different school-initiated activities. This implied that stakeholders participation and implementation of school based management should go hand in hand to achieve the goals and objectives of SBM.

CONCLUSION

Based on the data gathered, there were no single formula in achieving the overall goal of our school based management, however, there are number of practices that leads to positive and quality educational system these includes effective leadership, management strategies, faculty development and stakeholders participation. Therefore, with these practices, there is a huge probability that a school will likely achieve its goal.

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